

Research article

Two autumn collecting expeditions highlight the under-researched Lepidoptera fauna of Albania: new records and notes on related literature with additions to the fauna of the country (Lepidoptera: Macroheterocera)

Botond Balogh^{1,2,3}, Balázs Tóth⁴, Áron Horváth⁵, Stoyan Beshkov⁶, Nimród Varga^{7,8}

(1) [Corresponding author] Hungarian National Museum Public Collections Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Department of Zoology, Lepidoptera Collection, H-1088, Budapest, Baross utca 13, Hungary

(2) Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Science, H-111, Budapest, Pázmány Péter sétány 1, Hungary

(3) ArtEnto Foundation & Hungarian Entomological Society – Young Entomologists' Club, H-1088, Budapest, Bródy S. utca 32. 1/19, Hungary, balogh.botond@nhmus.hu

(4) Hungarian National Museum Public Collections Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Department of Zoology, Lepidoptera Collection, H-1088, Budapest, Baross utca 13, Hungary, toth.balazs@nhmus.hu

(5) ArtEnto Foundation & Hungarian Entomological Society – Young Entomologists' Club, H-1088, Budapest, Bródy S. utca 32. 1/19, Hungary, horvath2006aron@gmail.com

(6) National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, stoyan.beshkov@gmail.com

(7) University of Veterinary Medicine Budapest, H-1078, Budapest, István utca 2, Hungary

(8) ArtEnto Foundation & Hungarian Entomological Society – Young Entomologists' Club, H-1088, Budapest, Bródy S. utca 32. 1/19, Hungary, kaanzp@student.univet.hu

Abstract: The results of two entomological expeditions conducted in September–October 2025 near Mali me Gropa (Central Albania) concerning Macroheterocera are presented. One genus and three species are new for Albania, nine species are reported for the second time from the country. Among the new species, *Gortyna borelii lunata* (Freyer, 1838) is from Appendices II and IV of the EEC 92/43 Habitats Directive, while *Nothocasis rosariae* Scalercio, Infusino & Hausmann, 2016 is recorded for the second time from the Balkan Peninsula. The highest altitudes and the southernmost observation of *Gortyna borelii lunata* are also presented. For thirty other species, third and fourth reports for Albania are announced. Comprehensive literature sources are gathered to all 122 reported species.

Keywords: Albania, faunistics, Geometridae, Lepidoptera, Noctuidae, protected species

Introduction

Albania, situated on the southwest part of the Balkan Peninsula, is a country with exquisite and well-preserved natural habitats. Given these conditions, it also has a large and diverse Lepidoptera fauna. One of the first insights into this diversity was given by Rebel (1913), who published the results of several different collecting trips in the country. The first checklist, or even a catalogue, dealing exclusively with the Lepidoptera of Albania was the work of Rebel & Zerny (1931). Literature from the following years is scarce.

The expedition of 1961 by the German Entomological Institute ignited the renewal of scientific research on the Lepidoptera fauna of the country, providing considerable increase in the number of species known from the region (Fries, 1967). Professor Kastriot Misja (1933–2022) was a key person in Albanian entomology. Vast majority of his works circled around Lepidoptera giving a stable base to recent understanding of the butterfly and moth fauna of the country (Misja, 1976, 1978, 1980). In recent years, an increasing number of studies have been published on the Lepidoptera of Albania. Butterflies (Papilionoidea), being the most thoroughly

Fig. 1. The distribution map of nighttime collecting localities.

studied among them, are covered in several checklists such as the works of Verovnik & Popović (2013) and Cuvelier et al. (2018), with the most recent compilation by Bjerregård et al. (2023). In terms of nocturnal species, Stoyan Beshkov is responsible for the exceptional increase in research from Albania in recent times (Beshkov, 1994, 1995, 1996, 2018; Beshkov & Nahirić, 2018a; 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020a, 2024; Beshkov & Nahirić-Beshkova, 2021, 2025). His work contributed to the discovery of several species new to the fauna of the country, forming the base of a future checklist regarding the Lepidoptera of Albania. While his articles primarily revolve around Macroheterocera, a work on the informal group “Microlepidoptera” is already in progress (Plant, 2023). It is expected to be the first comprehensive list of Albania’s micromoths.

In the autumn of 2025, an expedition was conducted by the authors Nimród Varga, Áron Horváth and Botond Balogh between 9th and 13th October in the vicinity of Mali me Gropa, a limestone massif situated

in Tiranë County, central Albania. A few weeks prior, on 22nd September, Stoyan Beshkov spent a night collecting in the central part of the massif. The aim of that visit was to search for *Antitype suda schimae* Schawerda, 1911, a species he found in a similar-looking locality in Bosnia and Herzegovina at the beginning of September in the same year, but has not been recorded from Albania at that time. The aim of this article is to present the results of the two trips concerning Macroheterocera, with a particular focus on nocturnal species, providing further insight into Albania’s Lepidoptera fauna.

Material and methods

Hungarian team: Daytime search was carried out between two lakes, Liqeni i Shkallës and Liqeni i Bizës with samples collected around the nearby roads. Unlike the explorations during the day, nighttime

Fig. 2. The sight of the main sheet in operation on location B.

surveys were restricted to a limited area each night (Fig. 1).

Several devices focused on the attraction of nighttime flying moths. Each day two white sheets were illuminated with UV lights. The main sheet was illuminated by a few metres of 5 and 12V, 395 and 365nm UV LED strips, a 20W UV-A 368nm Sylvania bulb and 9 and 12V 365nm compact lights (Fig. 2). A second, simpler sheet was used for the purpose of greater area coverage. Illuminated by two 365nm UV flashlights, this sheet was put on branches or rock walls not far from the main light source. The only exception was on the third day when a third small sheet was also put up beside the road SH54 on a rock wall illuminated by UV flashlights and one rolled up UV LED strip. This sheet attracted the highest number of moths that day until it was stolen by the passenger of the only car using the road during the nighttime collecting. Alongside the light sources, ten

sugar ropes were deployed on branches at locations B and D. The use of these ropes, rinsed in mashed fruits and sugar, pinpointed the presence of certain species that are not responsive to light, thereby expanding the species list. Nighttime search was also performed with headlamps nearby the light sources, but outside their illuminated areas. Each location differed in their environmental setting.

Site A (elevation: 933 metres, exact location: 41°20'35.9"N 20°04'18.2"E) was located on the steep southern edge of Mali me Gropa on an isolated spot of vegetation surrounded by limestone walls and scree (Fig. 3A). The main sheet was put up on the grass, while the second sheet was placed on the limestone wall facing south. The sheets were operated from 09.10.2025 dusk to 10.10.2025 00:15.

Site B (elevation: 957 metres, exact location: 41°20'29.6"N 20°03'19.3"E) was located on an open shrubland with scattered pine trees (*Pinus* spp.) (Fig.

Fig. 3. The view of the collecting sites. A, location A; B, location B; C, location C; D, location D.

3B). The main sheet was put up in a more open area of the location, while the supplementary sheet was placed approximately 40 metres away on a dead branch in a more enclosed space surrounded by pine trees, causing the almost complete absence of any other plants. Baits were placed nearby on branches of trees and shrubs. The collecting period was on 10.10.2025 from dusk to 23:30.

Site C (elevation: 1380 metres, exact location: 41°21'34.1"N 20°01'39.5"E) was a rocky grassland higher than the previous two localities, with fresh herbaceous vegetation and a complete lack of live bushes and trees above the road SH54 (Fig. 3C). This phenomenon was not only the effect of the altitude, grazing or a lack of nutrition in the soil, but it was mainly caused by a recent fire that was indicated by the dead and burnt remains of bushes and trees and a

distinct layer of ash on the surface of the ground. The sheets used that day were placed in a 40-metre radius from each other above the road, on 11.10.2025 from dusk to 21:20.

Site D (elevation: 1395 metres, exact location: 41°20'21.1"N 20°08'07.8"E) was also located on a higher altitude rocky grassland, but there were no signs of fire (Fig. 3D). The main sheet was put up above a hornbeam tree (*Carpinus betulus* L.). The supplementary sheet was placed on a branch approximately 300 metres eastward in the first continuous forest above the road. Baits were also used that day 40 metres below the main sheet. The collecting period lasted from 18:40 to 23:00 on 12.10.2025.

The species were photographed, and their abundance was noted in the field. Adults of particular faunistic importance or not identifiable in field were

Fig. 4. The view of the collecting sites and devices. A, locality of Stoyan Beshkov, Mali me Gropa, near Nomad, 22.09.2025; B, portable light trap; C, Finnish tent-like trap; D, the view of location SB during the day.

collected and deposited in the Lepidoptera Collection of the Hungarian National Museum Public Collections Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest and in the private collection of Áron Horváth. Genitalia slides were prepared via the standard method, stained with eosine and mounted in Euparal. The slides were photographed with an Olympus SZX12 photographic microscope.

Stoyan Beshkov: Conducted a nighttime survey on 22.09.2025. The collecting methods have involved two portable light traps with an 8W “Blacklight” white tube (368 nm), powered by 12V 9Ah batteries as well as a Finnish “tent trap” with a 160W MV bulb at the top of the pole and a 20W (368 nm) black light lamp over the catching pot below, onwards the Finnish “tent trap” was furnished with LepiLED, a 1.5 maxi model UV LED lamp with adapter and transformer 220 – 12V, powered by a generator. An

additional EntoLight UV LED E27-300mm 8W 365–375nm and 395–405nm, 12W with transformer lamp was also positioned about 70–90 m from the tent trap. The maximum distance between the light traps was ca. 400 metres, as they were deployed with different outlooks wherever possible. All traps ran throughout the night, on 22.09.2025 from dusk to the dawn of 23.09.2025.

Site SB (elevation: 1491 metres, exact location: 41°22'05.9"N 20°03'09.0"E) was located south of the plateau near the Nomad Lake. This locality was a limestone area with dolines and mountain steppe with *Thalictrum*, *Verbascum*, and other, low growing vegetation. Part of the area located south-southeast of the road leading into the doline zone was burned in the summer of the same year. The location was situated between those of the Hungarian team, but norther (Fig. 4A–D).

Fig. 5. The temperature shifts on different locations visited by the Hungarian team during the nights.

Specimens and collecting localities were photographed with a Sony DSChX400v digital camera, the portable light trap was captured with a Samsung A30 S Android mobile phone. Genitalia were extracted and mounted on glass slides in Euparal after staining with a 2% Merbromin solution. All genitalia slides were photographed with a Zeiss stereo microscope Stemi 2000-C with Canon 2000 digital camera. The illustrated everted vesicae, and in some cases the female genitalia were photographed in alcohol before mounting on glass in Euparal. The genitalia slides and collected specimens are part of the collection of S. Beshkov in the NMNHS (National Museum of Natural History, Sofia). The number of specimens from locality SB indicates the material in the collection of Stoyan Beshkov in NMNHS. Otherwise, field observations are reported. The trip was self-financed and undertaken in holiday time.

Results

During the four days of the expedition conducted in October several locations were visited near Mali me Gropa and their Lepidoptera fauna was in the centre of attention. The daytime observations accumulated to a smaller fraction of the total number of species

found during the given timeframe. Varying environmental conditions contributed to the various results observed on the collecting sites. These differences are primarily driven by temperature contrasts associated with elevation and vegetation density, while wind also having notable influence (McGeachie, 1989) (Fig. 5).

Lepidoptera families and the order of the Sphingidae and the Lasiocampidae list are arranged according to Ronkay et al. (2024). The sequence and nomenclature of families Erebidae and Noctuidae follow Fibiger et al. (2011), with changes incorporated from subsequent taxonomic revisions and the recently published books of Top-Jensen et al. (2023) and Ronkay et al. (2024). The Geometridae are arranged according to Müller et al. (2019). The days of occurrence for species on or near given sites addressed by capital letters are the same as the operation dates stated in the material and methods, unless stated otherwise.

Order Lepidoptera Linnaeus, 1758
 Family Lasiocampidae Harris, 1841
 Subfamily Lasiocampinae Harris, 1841

Lasiocampa trifolii (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775).
 Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks.

The species can be found in the work of Rebel & Zerny (1931) and generally considered common across Albania (Misja, 1978; Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov et al., 2020a).

Macrothylacia rubi (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: Approximately 20 larvae near location C. Found feeding beside the road SH54 during the night. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already mention the species from Albania. Additional data were later provided regarding the distribution of the species in the country (Misja, 1978; Beshkov & Misja, 1995; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Family Brahmaeidae Swinhoe, 1892

Subfamily Lemoniinae Hampson, 1918

Lemonia strigata Antoshin & Zolotuhin, 2011. Material: Approximately 9 adults on location B, 6 on location C and 5 on location D. Arrived to the main sheet on sites B and D and to all the sheets on location C. Remarks. According to Prozorov et al. (2022), in Albania only *Lemonia strigata* is present from the taxa closely related to *Lemonia taraxaci* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Rebel & Zerny (1931) and Misja (1978) mention *L. taraxaci* from the country, but these are likely *Lemonia strigata* observations. Beshkov (1995) refers to the species as “*Lemonia taraxaci strigata* Rebel, 1910”. Later reports only mention *L. strigata* and question the credibility of previous *L. taraxaci* observations from the country (Nahirić & Beshkov, 2017; Beshkov & Nahirić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirić-Beshkova, 2021, 2025).

Family Sphingidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Macroglossinae Harris, 1839

Macroglossum stellatarum (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 3 adults near Liqeni i Shkallës (41°19'41.3"N 19°57'47.2"E) on 09.10.2025, 3 near Shëngjin (41°19'03.1"N 20°04'08.5"E) on 10.10.2025 and also 3 near location C. Observed in flight during the day. Remarks. The species appears in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Eichler & Friese (1965), Misja (1978), Beshkov (1994) and Bond (2023) also mention the species with additional records across Albania. The reason behind the lack of recent data might be caused by the focus towards Papilionoidea in publications on daytime-flying

Lepidoptera and lack of scientific interest in the country towards economically insignificant abundant species.

Hyles euphorbiae (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 1 larva near Liqeni i Shkallës (41°19'41.3"N 19°57'47.2"E) on 09.10.2025. Found feeding on *Euphorbia* sp. during the day. Remarks. Appears in the publication by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Several publications provided additional information regarding the species in the country (Eichler & Friese, 1965; Misja, 1978; Beshkov, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Plóciennik et al., 2009; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Family Geometridae Leach, 1815

Subfamily Ennominae Duponchel, 1845

Dicrognophos sartata (Treitschke, 1827). Material: Approximately 5 adults on location A and 4 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets. Remarks. The species appears in the work of Rebel (1913), Rebel & Zerny (1931) and numerous other articles from the country indicating its well-established presence in Albania (Moucha, 1963b; Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1990; Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov & Misja, 1995; Nahirić & Beshkov, 2017; Beshkov & Nahirić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b; Beshkov & Nahirić-Beshkova, 2021, 2025).

Ennomos quercaria (Hübner, 1813) (Fig. 6F). Material: 1 female on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. Even though Rebel & Zerny (1931) mention the species from “Albania”, the location “Jezero Kar bei Vunsaj”, referring to a lake near the village Vusanje is located in current day Montenegro. Therefore, its first published observation from Albania is linked to the work of Urbahn (1966). No other reported occurrence is known from the country. Second report for Albania. Distribution. Western Palearctic. Found mainly in the Mediterranean region, but the species bears data from non-Mediterranean parts of Central and Eastern Europe (Müller et al., 2019).

Campaea margaritaria (Linnaeus, 1761). Material: 3 adults on location A and 1 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on the first mentioned location and to the main sheet on location B. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already mentioned the species from Albania. Later reports

Fig. 6. Geometridae from Albania. A, *Nothocasis rosariae*; B, *Euphyia frustata*; C, *Colostygia wolfschlaegerae*; D, *Nebula senectaria*; E, *Nothocasis rosariae*, live specimen; F, *Ennomos quercaria*, live specimen. Scale bar to Figs A–D: 10 mm. Photos by Balázs Tóth (A–C), Stoyan Beshkov (D) and Áron Horváth (E, F).

reveal additional data on the species from the country (Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Charissa obscurata (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 1 male on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2453). Remarks. The species can be found in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). The following decades bear no published observation of *C. obscurata*. The second report only dates to 2019 when the species appeared in the work of Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a). Other reports are published by Beshkov et al. (2020a) and Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova (2021). The finding is stated as second report in the latter work. Even though the records are older than those in the previous two articles, due to the publication year being 2021 it cannot be considered as such.

Charissa variegata (Duponchel, 1830). Material: 4 adults on location A and 3 near location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on location A and to the supplementary sheet on location B. Genitalia of two males were examined (Gen. preps TB2469, TB2475). Remarks. The species can be found in the publication by Rebel & Zerny (1931). After decades without published sighting from Albania, the species reappeared in the work of Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a). Additional reports provide valuable information regarding the distribution of the species in the country (Beshkov et al., 2020b; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021).

Charissa supinaria (Mann, 1854). Material: 2 adults on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Genitalia of one female was examined (Gen. prep. TB2470). Remarks. The species appears in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931) and was also found by the German Entomological Institute (Urbahn, 1966). It appears to be widespread in Albania (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021, 2025; Beshkov et al., 2024). The possibility of previous misidentification of the species in articles from the country as *Charissa glaucinaria* (Hübner, 1799) is well detailed by Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova (2021).

Peribatodes rhomboidaria (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: Approximately 5 adults on locations A and B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each mentioned location. Remarks. First appearing in the work of Rebel & Zerny (1931), the species is generally considered as common in Albania (Moucha, 1963b;

Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov et al., 1996, 2020b; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a).

Peribatodes umbraria (Hübner, 1809). Material: 1 adult on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) mention the species in their checklist from the country. Many additional reports are linked to *P. umbraria* from Albania (Misja, 1977; Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020a, 2020b).

Peribatodes correptaria (Zeller, 1847). Material: Approximately 10 adults on location A and 1 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on location A and to the main sheet on location B. Remarks. Even though numerous specimens were found during the trip, the reported observations regarding the species are scarce. It was first reported from the country by Beshkov et al. (1996) and the sole other publication mentioning its occurrence was published by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a). Third report for Albania. Distribution. Western Palearctic. From Italy throughout the Balkans, Ukraine, Turkey, Lebanon and Jordan to Israel (Müller et al., 2019).

Opisthograptis luteolata (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 5 adults on location A and 4 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each mentioned location. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already refer to the species from Albania. Currently it is known from several locations across the country (Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Subfamily Sterrhinae Meyrick, 1892

Idaea seriata (Schrank, 1802). Material: 1 adult in Shëngjin (41°19'21.5"N 20°04'18.1"E) on 11.10.2025. Found resting during the day. Remarks. The species already appears in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Even though Urbahn (1966) and Misja (1977) mention *I. seriata* from several locations, the species has no recent data published. Fourth report for Albania.

Idaea camparia sodaliaria (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852). Material: 6 adults on location A and 1 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on location A and to the main sheet on location B. Genitalia of one male was examined (Gen. prep. TB2460). Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already mention the species from

Albania. Urbahn (1966) added two new localities to the distribution of *I. camparia*. The latest report by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) provided two more observations with additional localities from the country. Fourth report for Albania.

Idaea degeneraria (Hübner, 1799). Material: 1 adult near location A. Arrived to the supplementary sheet. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. The species can be found in the work of Rebel & Zerny (1931) and in numerous other articles (Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov et al., 1996, 2020b; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a).

Scopula ornata (Scopoli, 1763). Material: 1 adult on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already mention this species from several locations. Additional records accumulated to the better understanding of the distribution of *S. ornata* in the country (Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b; Bond, 2023).

Scopula incanata (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks. The oldest report for Albania is that of Rebel (1913). Several records followed proving the constant presence of the species in the country (Rebel & Zerny, 1931; Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov et al., 2020a, 2020b).

Scopula submutata (Treitschke, 1828). Material: Approximately 3 adults on location A and 2 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each mentioned location. Genitalia of one male was examined (Gen. prep. TB2468). Remarks. This species is also found in the work of Rebel & Zerny (1931). Further data about the species from Albania can be found in the article of Urbahn (1966), Beshkov & Misja (1995), Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) and Beshkov et al. (2020b).

Scopula imitaria (Hübner, 1799). Material: 1 adult on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. The species is present in the work of Rebel & Zerny (1931). The number of additional reports and recorded specimens suggest that it is widely distributed and common in the country (Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov & Misja, 1995; Beshkov et al., 1996, 2020b; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a).

Scopula marginepunctata (Goeze, 1781). Material: Approximately 10 adults on location A, 5 on location B and 1 on location D. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on location A and B and to the main sheet on location D. Remarks. The species is

mentioned in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) consider the species as common in Albania. The number of other records supports this statement (Moucha, 1963b; Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Subfamily Larentiinae Duponchel, 1845

Aplocera plagiata (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 2 adults on locations A and D. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on location A and to the main sheet on location D. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already mention the species as part of the Albanian fauna backed by several records. Its occurrence in the country is further documented by additional publications (Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Nothocasis rosariae Scalercio, Infusino & Hausmann, 2016 (Figs 6A, E, 7A). Material: 1 male near location B. Arrived to the supplementary sheet. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2452). Remarks. In the original description by Scalercio et al. (2016) *Fagus sylvatica* (L.) was hypothesised as potential hostplant. This theory was later disproved by Greco et al. (2019) recognising *Acer* spp. as hostplant similarly to its sister species *Nothocasis sertata* (Hübner, 1817). While additional data from southern Italy where the type locality is located kept appearing soon after the description of *N. rosariae*, the single male specimen from Greece mentioned by Scalercio et al. (2016) remained the only known representative of its species from the Balkan Peninsula (Infusino et al., 2017; Scalercio & Greco, 2018). This data scarcity might be caused by lack of research conducted in the mountainous forests of the southern regions with high number of *Acer* spp. during the autumnal period. New genus and species for Albania, second report for the Balkan Peninsula and northernmost observation of *N. rosariae*. Distribution. Previously known only from Italy and Greece (Scalercio et al., 2016).

Scotopteryx bipunctaria (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) (Fig. 7G). Material: 1 female on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2471). Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931), Urbahn (1966) and Misja (1977) all mention the species from several locations, but it ceased to appear in the following publications. The only recent report from Albania by Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova (2021) mentions only one specimen.

Fig. 7. Genitalia of Geometridae from Albania. A, *Nothocasis rosariae*, slide No. TB2452m; B, *Colostygia wolfschlaegerae*, slide No. TB2465m; C, *Nebula senectaria*, slide No. GP1.04.III.2026; D, *Eupithecia ericeata*, slide No. GP3.04.III.2026; E, *Eupithecia semigraphata*, slide No. GP2.04.III.2026; F, *Euphyia frustata*, slide No. TB2451f; G, *Scotopteryx bipunctaria*, slide No. TB2471f; H, *Eupithecia ericeata*, slide No. GP1.05.III.2026. Scale bar: 1 mm. Photos by Botond Balogh (A, B, F, G) and Stoyan Beshkov (C–E, H).

Camptogramma bilineata (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 3 adults on locations A and B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each mentioned location. Remarks. The species can be found in the checklist compiled by Rebel & Zerny (1931). *Camptogramma bilineata* is currently known from many different locations across Albania (Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Epirrhoe galiata (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks. The oldest report for Albania is that of Rebel & Zerny (1931). Additional reports from the country subsequently followed (Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Euphyia frustata (Treitschke, 1828) (Figs 6B, 7F). Material: 1 female on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2451). Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) mentioned the species from the country. Additional reports followed, some noting unusual colouration, from which the specimen of the present study is no exception (Urbahn, 1966; Beshkov et al., 2020b, 2024; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021).

Pennithera firmata (Hübner, 1822). Material: 2 adults on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets. Remarks. First reported from Albania by Misja (1990). The sole other article mentioning the species from the country was published by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a). Third report for Albania. Distribution. Western Palearctic. Found across Europe from Portugal to western parts of European Russia. The species is also present in northern Türkiye and in the Caucasus (Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012).

Dysstroma truncata (Hufnagel, 1767). Material: 1 adult on location B and 1 near Liqeni i Bizës (41°19'43.0"N 20°10'07.5"E) on 12.10.2025. Arrived to the main sheet on location B and caught in flight during the day on the other location. Remarks. Similarly to *P. firmata*, this species was also published first for the country by Misja (1990). Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova (2021) contributed with the second report. Third report for Albania. Distribution. Holarctic. In Europe, the species is found from the British Isles to the Ural Mountains. It lives at higher altitudes in the south. Outside Europe, the species is known from the Caucasus region, Turkey, Russia, China and Japan. A subspecies, *Dysstroma truncata traversata* (Kellcott, 1886) is found in North America as well (Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012).

Colostygia wolfschlaegerae (Pinker, 1953) (Figs 6C, 7B). Material: 1 male on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2465). Remarks. The species was reported as new for the Albanian Lepidoptera fauna recently by Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova (2025). No further publication mentions its occurrence in the country. Second report for Albania. Distribution. The species is found in the southern Balkans and north-eastern Turkey (Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012).

Coenotephria ablutaria probaria (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852). Material: Approximately 20 adults on location A and 10 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets. Genitalia of one male was examined (Gen. prep. TB2467). 3 males were also found on location SB. Remarks. In Albania, according to Hausmann (2011) and Müller et al. (2019), this subspecies can be found. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) reported the species as new to Albania and Beshkov et al. (2020b) even contribute with a “second report”. Previous articles mention “*Coenotephria salicata* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)” from the country, however *C. ablutaria* was its synonym for a long period. For example, Rebel & Zerny (1931) added the phrase “Form *ablutaria*” to their “*C. salicata*” observations and Urbahn (1966) stated that “Form *ablutaria*” is not always clearly defined. The locality Borsh, mentioned by Urbahn (1966), is a seashore village, with habitats more suitable for *C. ablutaria* than the other species. In conclusion, all mention of *Coenotephria salicata* from the country presumably refer to *Coenotephria ablutaria*.

Nebula senectaria (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852) (Figs 6D, 7C). Material: 1 male on location SB (Gen. prep. 1./04.III.2026, S. Beshkov). Remarks. The differences between *Nebula senectaria*, *Nebula nebulata* (Treitschke, 1828), *Nebula pirinica* (Reisser, 1936) and *Nebula achromaria* (la Harpe, 1853) are very moderate both in external appearance and in genitalia (males). In Albania *Nebula senectaria* is known only from Plani i Bardhë (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a). Second report for Albania. Distribution. In Europe the species can be found in Italy and the Balkan Peninsula, but its eastern distribution stretches as far as the Caucasus and Israel (Hausmann & Viidalepp, 2012).

Horisme vitalbata (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 1 adult near location A. Arrived to the supplementary sheet. Remarks. Mentioned in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Additional data suggest the constant presence of this species in

Albania (Urbahn, 1966; Misja, 1977; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020a, 2020b).

Eupithecia ericeata (Rambur, 1833) (Figs 7D, 7H). Material: 1 female on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2458). 3 males and 5 females were also found on location SB and their genitalia were also examined (Gen. prep. 3./04.III.2026, S. Beshkov; Gen. prep. 1./05.III.2026, S. Beshkov). Remarks. Even though Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) reported the species from several locations across Albania with numerous specimens, their finding remained the only reported encounter of the species from the country until now. Second report for Albania. Distribution. The species is found from Spain to southern Russia in Europe, mainly in the Mediterranean region, but reaching up to the Czech Republic. Outside Europe, the species is found in Asian parts of Turkey (Mironov, 2003).

Eupithecia semigraphata Bruand, 1847 (Fig. 7E). Material: Approximately 40 specimens on location A and 5 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets. Genitalia of two females were examined (Gen. preps TB2459, TB2466). 1 male was also found on location SB. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. 2./04.III.2026, S. Beshkov). Remarks. The species can be found in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Misja (1990) also mentions *E. semigraphata* from the country. The latest encounter is published by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a). Fourth report for Albania.

Family Erebidae Leach, 1815

Subfamily Hypeninae Herrich-Schäffer, 1851

Hypena lividalis (Hübner, 1796). Material: 1 adult on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. The species is in the checklist compiled by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Heinicke (1965) referred to the previously published data without newly recorded specimen. Additional reports reveal several new locations for this species in the country (Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025).

Subfamily Boletobiinae Guenée, 1858

Eublemma ostrina (Hübner, 1808). Material: 1 adult on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. Similarly to the previous species, *E. ostrina* is found

in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931) and also mentioned in the work of Heinicke (1965) without new data. Multiple reports were published since regarding *E. ostrina* (Misja, 1980; Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov et al., 1996, 2020b; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025).

Eublemma purpurina (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 1 adult near Liqeni i Shkallës (41°19'41.3"N 19°57'47.2"E) on 09.10.2025. Found resting in the vegetation during the day. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) mention the species from Albania. *E. purpurina* is known from several locations across the country (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov & Misja, 1995; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Subfamily Arctiinae Leach, 1815

Setina irrorella (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks. In the country, the species is known from Tomor (Rebel & Zerny, 1931) and Vermosh (Misja, 1978). Third report for Albania. Distribution. *S. irrorella* is a widespread species with Palearctic distribution. Found from Spain to the southern parts of Russia (Macià et al., 2025).

Dysauxes famula (Freyer, 1836). Material: 2 adults on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets. Remarks. Since this species was a synonym for *Dysauxes punctata* (Fabricius, 1781) for a protracted period, identification of the species in older literature is difficult. Rebel & Zerny (1931) mention “*Dysauxes hyalina* ab. *famula* Frr.” which almost certainly refers to *D. famula*. Misja (1990) only mentions *D. punctata*, but from several locations and no further mention of this species occurs in literature from Albania. The determination of whether any of the data provided could be record for *D. famula* is impossible without the examination of specimens, as both species might be present in the country according to Ignatyev & Zolotuhin (2006). The only recent data regarding *D. famula* from Albania is provided by Beshkov et al. (2020a).

Subfamily Toxocampinae Guenée, 1852

Lygephila cracca (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 5 adults on location A and 4 on location B. Ar-

rived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each location and also to bait on location B. Remarks. Plóciennik et al. (2009) reported the species as new to the fauna of Albania, even though it was previously mentioned by Rebel & Zerny (1931), Heinicke (1965) and Misja (1980). Recent records are provided by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) and Beshkov et al. (2020b).

Lygephila procax (Hübner, 1813). Material: 1 adult on location A and 6 on location B. Arrived to the main sheet on location A and to both the main and supplementary sheets and bait on location B. Remarks. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b) reported the species first from Albania. Later found in several locations across the country (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020a, 2020b, 2024).

Apopestes spectrum (Esper, 1787). Material: 2 adults near location B, 1 in Shëngjin inside a private apartment (41°19'22.1"N 20°04'18.7"E) on 11.10.2025 and 3 in Burimas inside a small cave (41°20'29.7"N 20°03'54.8"E) on 12.10.2025. Arrived to bait on location B and found resting during the day on the other locations. Remarks. This species is already mentioned in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Heinicke (1965) mentions the species from Albania but only refers to the data published previously. Further records of the species can only be found in two articles from the country, presumably due to its rare appearance on light sources and not because its rarity (Misja, 1976; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a).

Subfamily Erebiinae Leach, 1815

Catocala elocata (Esper, 1787). Material: 2 adults on location A and 1 on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Also found on location SB. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already report the species from Albania. Further mention by Heinicke (1965) provided no additional data. Misja (1976) however contributed with several new records from different localities. The latest report from the country is linked to Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) mentioning the species as a common member of the Albanian fauna.

Family Noctuidae Latreille, 1809

Subfamily Plusiinae Boisduval, 1829

Chrysodeixis chalcites (Esper, 1789). Material: 1 adult on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. The

species appears to be abundant in Albania as it can be found in several publications from the country (Rebel & Zerny, 1931; Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994; Kullaj et al., 2005; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b; Bond, 2023).

Autographa gamma (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 1 adult on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. This migratory species appears to be widespread in the country as it was mentioned in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931) and many other works (Moucha, 1963b; Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Kullaj et al., 2005; Plóciennik et al., 2009; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b; Bond, 2023).

Subfamily Acontiinae Guenée, 1841

Anophia leucomelas (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks. The oldest report for Albania is that of Rebel & Zerny (1931) for Tirana and Miloti. The species was later reportedly observed in several other locations (Heinicke, 1965; Beshkov, 1995; Nahirnić & Beshkov, 2017; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020a).

Subfamily Acronictinae Harris, 1841

Acronicta euphorbiae (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 1 larva near location D. Found feeding on *Euphorbia* sp. around sunset. Remarks. The species was first reported from Albania by Misja (1980). Rebel & Zerny (1931) also mention *A. euphorbiae* as part of the "Albanian" fauna, but the locations given are not part of the country as explained by Beshkov (1995). Reliable additional data surfaced recently (Beshkov et al., 2020a, 2020b; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021).

Subfamily Cuculliinae Herrich-Schäffer, 1850

Cucullia formosa Rogenhofer, 1860 (Figs 12A–B). Material: Approximately 20 larvae near location A and another 12 near location C below the road where the fire did not affect the vegetation. The specimens near site C were observed on two days: 10–11.10.2025 feeding on *Artemisia* sp. both during the

night and the day. Remarks. The species was first reported from the country by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018a) from Shkallë and for the second time by Beshkov et al. (2020a) from Mali me Gropa between locations A and C and from Plani i Bardhë near Bulqizë Town. Its presence was deemed unexpected in the initial publication from the country, but the species appears to have stable populations in the vicinity of Mali me Gropa. Third report for Albania. Distribution. The species has a sporadic distribution across Europe. It is known from France, Italy, Hungary, Slovenia, Serbia, Bulgaria, Albania, Greece and North Macedonia (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018a). Kranjčev (1999) mentions the species from Croatia as well. Outside Europe, according to Ronkay & Ronkay (1994), this species can also be found in the Asian steppe region, although sporadically.

Cucullia tanaceti (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 1 larva near location C on 10.10.2025. Found feeding on *Artemisia* sp. during the day. Remarks. First reported from the country by Misja (1980). The only other known Albanian record of the species is provided by Beshkov et al. (2024). Third report for Albania. Distribution. The species is widely distributed in Europe and can be found in dry steppe and mountainous regions except the British Isles, the north-western Atlantic coast and northern Scandinavia. Outside Europe the species can be found in the North African coast and western Asia (Ronkay & Ronkay, 1994).

Subfamily Oncocnemidinae Forbes & Franclemont, 1954

Praestilbia armeniaca Staudinger, 1892. Material: Around 10 adults on location A and 2 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each location. Remarks. It was first reported from Albania by Beshkov & Misja (1995). The occurrence of the species has been documented in several locations since, but not in Mali me Gropa (Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025).

Subfamily Amphipyrinae Guenée, 1838

Amphipyra effusa (Boisduval, 1828). Material: 1 adult near location A. Caught in flight not far from the

main sheet but it flew not towards the light sources. Remarks. The species appears in the checklist compiled by Rebel & Zerny (1931). It has been reported from several locations so far from Albania (Misja, 1980; Beshkov et al., 1996, 2024; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b; Naumova, 2020; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025).

Amphipyra tragopoginis (Clerck, 1759). Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks. The oldest report for Albania is that of Rebel & Zerny (1931) from Beshtriku. Other reported occurrences followed significantly later (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018b, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Amphipyra pyramidea (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 1 adult on location A and 1 near location B. Arrived to the main sheet on site A and to bait on site B. Remarks. Rebel (1913) already mentions the species as part of the Albanian fauna. It appears in several works from the country (Rebel & Zerny, 1931; Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a).

Subfamily Psaphidinae Grote, 1896

Meganephria bimaculosa (Linnaeus, 1767). Material: 2 adults on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. The species was first reported from the country by Misja (1980). Additional observations were published by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b, 2019a). Fourth report for Albania.

Allophytes oxyacanthae (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 2 adults near location D. Arrived to the supplementary sheet and to bait. Remarks. The species is in the checklist compiled by Rebel & Zerny (1931). It appears three more times in literature from the country (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a).

Subfamily Heliiothinae Boisduval, 1829

Helicoverpa armigera (Hübner, 1808). Material: 1 adult near location A. Arrived to the supplementary sheet. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already mention the species from Albania. Its constant presence in the country is backed by numerous articles (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994; Plóciennik et al., 2009; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Subfamily Eriopinae Herrich-Schäffer, 1851

Callopietria latreillei (Duponchel, 1828). Material: 5 adults on location A and 1 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on site A. The specimen on site B was found on the main sheet. Remarks. Mentioned in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). The species is known from numerous locations across Albania (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1980; Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov & Misja, 1995; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Subfamily Xyleninae Guenée, 1852

Spodoptera exigua (Hübner, 1808). Material: 1 adult on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. This migratory species appears in literature from Albania in many instances (Rebel & Zerny, 1931; Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1980; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Kullaj et al., 2005; Płóciennik et al., 2009; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Spodoptera littoralis (Boisduval, 1833). Material: 1 adult on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. The species was first reported from the country by Beshkov (1995). Recent research gives more data on the occurrence of this moth in Albania (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018b, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025).

Paradrina flavirena Guenée, 1852. Material: 1 female on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2474). Remarks. The species was reported as new to the Albanian fauna by Beshkov et al. (1996). Later reports mention the species from several locations across the country (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018b, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Paradrina clavipalpis (Scopoli, 1763). Material: 1 male on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2472). Remarks. The species is found in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). It appears to be widely distributed and common across Albania (Moucha, 1963b; Heinicke, 1965; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a). Misja (1980) only mentions *Paradrina selini* (Boisduval, 1840) from the country. Due to individual variations, some forms of these and other closely related species can be inseparable from each other without the examination of the genitalia, therefore

arising uncertainty for previous reports without genitalia examination.

Hoplodrina ambigua (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 3 adults on location A and 5 on location B. Arrived to the main and supplementary sheets on both locations. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. The species appears in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). It is known from several locations across Albania (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1980; Beshkov & Misja, 1995; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Thalpophila matura (Hufnagel, 1766). Material: 1 adult on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already mention the species from Albania. Its occurrence in the country is further documented by several publications (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov et al., 2020a). Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) also mention a species “*Thaupophila*” *matura* (Hufnagel, 1766) which certainly refers to *Thalpophila matura* and is a misspelling.

Phlogophora meticulosa (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 1 adult near location C. Arrived to the supplementary sheet on the dead branch. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. Appears in the publication by Rebel & Zerny (1931). The observations of this migratory species in the country are published in numerous articles (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a).

Gortyna flavago (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) (Fig. 8A). Material: 1 adult on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2020) reported the species and the genus as new for the country. No observation was published since. Second report for Albania. Distribution. The species has a wide distribution across western Eurasia, stretching from Portugal to western Siberia (Zilli et al., 2005).

Gortyna borelii lunata (Freyer, 1838) (Figs 8B–C, 12D). Material: 1 male on location D. Arrived to the main sheet. 1 female was also collected by Stoyan Beshkov near location SB on 22.09.2025. Remarks. The subspecies *lunata* is currently the only known subspecies from the Balkan Peninsula (Baranyi et al., 2006). The species does not have any previous data from the country. The habitat where the specimens of the present work were found most resembles the habitats of the Domogled, Romania (Rákossy et al., 2024). The reports from Bulgaria were also from similar habitats, but they were proven incorrect due to mislabelled specimens (Beshkov, 2013a, 2013b) from

Fig. 8. Noctuidae from Albania. A, *Gortyna flavago*; B, *Gortyna borelii lunata*, male; C, *Gortyna borelii lunata*, female; D, *Episema tersa*; E, *Dryobotodes eremita*; F, *Anchoscelis litura*; G, *Xylena lunifera*. Scale bar: 10 mm. Photos by Botond Balogh (A, B, F, G) and Stoyan Beshkov (C–E).

the collection of Al. Slivov in the Institute of Zoology, at present the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. The present findings mark the highest altitudes (1395–1491 metres) and southernmost observations of this species, which is strictly protected in the EU (Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC, Appendices II and IV) (Gyulai, 1987; Ringwood et al., 2002; Rákósy et al., 2024). These findings suggest the possible occurrence of

Gortyna borelii lunata in similar habitats in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Montenegro. New species for the fauna of Albania. Distribution. The species has large but localised distribution across Europe (Ringwood et al., 2004). This pattern suggests a previously continuous area where the species could have been found, but due to fragmentation of suitable habitats, the populations became isolated from each other (Zilli et al., 2005).

Mesapamea secalis (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 3 males on location SB. Genitalia examined. Remarks. In Albania, this species is known from Beshtriku, Rogozhina (Rebel & Zerny, 1931, Heinicke, 1965), Tirana (Misja, 1976), Ionian Sea Coast, Dhermi Village (Beshkov, 1995), Tomori (Beshkov et al., 2020a) and Shkallë (Beshkov et al., 2020b). It may have been confused in the past with *Mesapamea secalella* Remm, 1983, a species also present in Albania.

Episema tersa (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) (Fig. 8D). Material: 1 male below location A (41°20'30.6"N 20°04'14.4"E) on the day of nighttime collecting. Caught in flight by hand, after all equipment were packed away for the night. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2473). 2 males were also found on location SB. Remarks. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b) reported the species as new to the Albanian fauna. Further data are provided by the same authors (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021, 2025).

Cirroedia centrago (Haworth, 1809). Material: 1 adult on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. Its first observation in the country was published by Misja (1976). Additional data was provided by Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova (2021). Third report for Albania. Distribution. Throughout Europe from Portugal to Russia represented by the nominate subspecies. In Asia reaching as far as the western chains of Himalayas in the East, where several different subspecies can be found (Ronkay et al., 1990).

Tiliacea citrigo (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: 1 adult on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) reported its sole occurrence in Albania, and no further data is available about this species from the country. Second report for Albania. Distribution. A quite widespread European species, which can be found from the Pyrenees to the Urals, Caucasus and western Turkey (Ronkay et al., 1990).

Tiliacea aurago (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 2 adults on location A, 1 specimen on location B and 3 specimens on location D. Arrived to the main sheet on each location. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. The species was first mentioned in Albanian literature regarding Lepidoptera by Misja (1976). Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) reported the species the second time from the country. Third report for Albania. Distribution. Very

similar to *T. citrigo* but this species extends further north (Ronkay et al., 1990).

Tiliacea cypreago christiani (Fibiger, 1992). Material: 3 adults on location A and another 3 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each mentioned location. Remarks. Its initial finding in the country was reported by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a). Additional data were provided by Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova (2021, 2025). Fourth report for Albania.

Lithophane ornitopus (Hufnagel, 1766). Material: 1 adult on location D. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. First reported by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b) from Albania. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) provided further data with the second report of this species from the country. Third report for Albania. Distribution. Euro-Siberian. Found from Portugal to western Siberia (Ronkay et al., 1990; Pino Pérez et al., 2019).

Xylena lunifera (Warren, 1910) (Figs 8G, 12D). Material: 2 adults near location B. Arrived to bait. Remarks. Its first observation in the country was published by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018a). Additional data was provided by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a). Third report for Albania. Distribution. The species is found from the southern edge of the Carpathians across the Balkans and Turkey to the South Caucasus (Ronkay et al., 1990).

Conistra vaccinii (Linnaeus, 1761). Material: 3 adults near location D. Arrived to bait. Remarks. First reported from Albania by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b). Additional data was later provided by the same authors constituting the second record of this species in the country (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a). Third report for Albania. Distribution. The most widespread among all *Conistra* species. Found across Europe, North Africa along the shore of the Mediterranean Sea, Asia Minor, in the Near East, reaching the end of its eastern distribution in China and central Siberia on the steppes (Ronkay et al., 1990).

Conistra rubiginea (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 1 adult near location A, 1 on location B, 2 on location C and 1 near location D. Arrived to the main sheet on locations B and C, to the supplementary sheet on location A and to bait on location D. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. Even though this species appeared on all locations during the nights, its appearance in Albanian literature is scarce. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b, 2019a) were the only reporters of this species from the country. Third report for Albania. Distribution.

Widespread species. Found from Portugal across Europe to western Siberia (Ronkay et al., 1990).

Anchoscelis litura (Linnaeus, 1761) (Figs 8F, 10C). Material: 1 male on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2463). Remarks. The species was first reported from the country by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018c). Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova (2021) contributed with the second published observation. Third report for Albania. Distribution. Found across Europe reaching its northern limit in Central Sweden and Finland. The eastern border of its distribution is hard to determine as the separation is difficult from its sister species *Anchoscelis luteogrisea* (Warren, 1911), which reaches the western limit of its distribution in the Balkans (Ronkay et al., 1990).

Leptologia macilenta (Hübner, 1809). Material: 1 adult on location B and 10 on location D. Arrived to the main sheet on location B and to both the main and supplementary sheet on location D. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. As most of the species belonging to the autumn fauna, this one was also reported recently from Albania the first time (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018a). The species has two additional appearances in the literature from the country (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025). Fourth report for Albania.

Sunira circellaris (Hufnagel, 1766). Material: 5 adults on location D. Arrived to the main sheet. The species was also found on location SB. Remarks. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b) reported the species as new to Albania. The species' sole other report from the country was published by the same authors (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a). Third report for Albania. Distribution. The species can be found from Portugal across Europe to western Siberia, even reaching Iceland in the North (Ronkay et al., 1990).

Dryobotodes eremita (Fabricius, 1775) (Figs 8E, 10A). Material: 2 adults on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Genitalia of one male was examined (Gen. prep. TB2464). 1 female was also found on location SB. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. 2./18. XII.2025). Remarks. Even though Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b) reported the species as new to the Albanian fauna, another article of them (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018a) stating "second report" for this species has been published 1 month before, therefore involuntarily claiming the right for first report. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) also mention the species from the country. Fourth report for Albania.

Antitype chi (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 9A). Material: 1 adult on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a) reported the species as new to the Albanian fauna. Second report is that of Beshkov et al. (2020a). No further mention has surfaced since from the country. Third report for Albania. Distribution. The species has the widest distribution among the species in its genus, reaching from Portugal and the British Isles to Asia Minor and the Russian Far East (Ronkay et al., 1990).

Antitype suda schimae Schawerda, 1911 (Figs 9B–F, 10B, 10E–H, 12E). Material: 1 male on location A. Arrived to one of the two sheets. Genitalia examined (Gen. prep. TB2461). 52 males and 3 females were found on location SB. Genitalia of both sexes examined (Gen. preps S. Beshkov 1./07. XI.2025; 1./08. XII.2025; 2./08. XII.2025). Remarks. *Antitype suda schimae* is very variable, confusion with *Antitype jonis* (Lederer, 1865) is possible even after examination of the male genitalia. Examination of the everted vesica is recommended. The female genitalia are more diagnostic. The finding was expected, because on 01st September in a very similar looking locality in Bosnia and Herzegovina on a lower altitude, Stoyan Beshkov and Ana Nahirnić-Beshkova found several specimens of *Antitype suda schimae* at light. This suggested the possible occurrence of the species in Albania, Mali me Gropa, near the location SB. *Antitype jonis* can be found in the checklist compiled by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Heinicke (1965) reported that species from the same locality where the previously reported specimens were found. New localities were published recently (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021). Due to the finding of *A. suda schimae* in the country, these reports are considered doubtful, although the examination of the male genitalia of the reported specimens is possible after brushing. Ongoing revision might reveal additional subspecies or even species from this group. New species for Albania. Distribution. The species has a scattered distribution with a different subspecies on each fragment. Two are found in the Alps, one in the Apennines and the present subspecies is endemic to the Balkans (Ronkay et al., 1990; Mrnjavčić Vojvoda et al., 2014).

Ammoconia caecimacula (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 2 adults on location A, 3 on location B, 2 near location C and 3 on location D. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets

Fig. 9. *Antitype* spp. from Albania. A, *Antitype chi*; B–F, *Antitype suda schimae*, males; G–H, *Antitype suda schimae*, females. Scale bar: 10 mm. Photos by Balázs Tóth (A, B) and Stoyan Beshkov (C–H).

on locations A and B, to both supplementary sheets on location C and to the main sheet on location D. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. First reported from the country by Misja (1980). Additional information was provided by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018a, 2019a). Fourth report for Albania.

Ammoconia senex (Geyer, 1828). Material: 2 adults on location A, 6 on location C and 8 on location

D. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each given location. Remarks. Beshkov & Misja (1995) reported the species as new to Albania. Later mentioned in several articles (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018a, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021).

Trigonophora flammea (Esper, 1785). Material: 1 adult near location A and 2 on location B. Arrived to the supplementary sheet of location A, to the main

Fig. 10. Genitalia of Noctuidae from Albania. A, *Dryobotodes eremita*, slide No. GP2.18.XII.25; B, *Antitype suda schimae*, slide No. GP1.08.12.2025; C, *Anchoscelis litura*, slide No. TB2463m; D, *Antitype suda schimae*, slide No. TB2461m; E, *Antitype suda schimae*, slide No. GP1.7.11.2025; F, *Antitype suda schimae*, slide No. GP2.08.12.2025; G, *Antitype suda schimae*, everted vesica, slide No. GP1.7.11.2025; H, *Antitype suda schimae*, everted vesica, slide No. GP1.7.11.2025. Scale bar: 1 mm. Photos by Stoyan Beshkov (A, B, E–H) and Botond Balogh (C, D).

Fig. 11. Noctuidae from Albania. A, *Aporophyla lutulenta*; B–C, *Euxoa vitta herzegovinensis*, males; D, *Euxoa vitta herzegovinensis*, female; E, *Standfussiana lucerneae*; F, *Noctua tertia*, upperside; G, ditto, underside. Scale bars: 10 mm. Photos by Balázs Tóth (A) and Stoyan Beshkov (B–G).

sheet and bait on location B. Remarks. The initial finding of the species in the country was reported by Misja (1980). Further data on its distribution in Albania are provided in recent research articles (Nahirić & Beshkov, 2017; Beshkov & Nahirić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirić-Beshkova, 2025).

Aporophyla lutulenta (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) (Fig. 11A). Material: 1 adult on location D. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. The species only appears once in literature from the country in the work of Beshkov & Nahirić (2019a). Second report for Albania. Distribution. The species can be found

Fig. 12. Live individuals of Noctuidae from Albania. A, *Cucullia formosa*, larva, dorsal view; B *Cucullia formosa*, larva, lateral view; C, *Gortyna borelii lunata*, male adult; D, *Xylena lunifera*, adult; E, *Antitype suda schimae*, male adult; F, *Standfussiana lucerneae illyrica*, female adult. Photos by Áron Horváth (A–D, F) and Stoyan Beshkov (E).

from Italy across the southern regions of Central and Eastern Europe reaching the Caucasus and Asia Minor (Ronkay et al., 1990; Nowacki et al., 2023).

Aporophyla canescens (Duponchel, 1827).
Material: 8 adults on location A and 10 on location B.

Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each mentioned location. Genitalia of one male was examined (Gen. prep. TB2462). Remarks. This species already appears in the checklist compiled by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Numerous additional records

back the constant occurrence of the species in Albania (Heinicke, 1965; Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021).

Dasypolia templi vecchiontium Ronkay & Varga, 1985. Material: 1 adult near location A and 1 on location D. Arrived to the supplementary sheet on location A and to the main sheet on location D. Remarks. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b) reported the species from Albania for the first time. Further data are provided by Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova (2021, 2025). Fourth report for Albania.

Polymixis serpentina (Treitschke, 1825). Material: 5 adults on location A and 7 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each mentioned location and even to bait near site B. Remarks. Misja (1976) mentions the species for the first time from Albania. Several sightings were reported since (Beshkov, 1995; Nahirnić & Beshkov, 2017; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025).

Polymixis rufocincta (Geyer, 1828). Material: 1 adult on location C and 8 on location D. Arrived to the main sheet on each location. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already mention this species from Albania. Additional data is also available regarding *P. rufocincta* from the country (Heinicke, 1965; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018b, 2019a).

Mesogona acetosellae (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 1 adult on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. This species is mentioned in Albanian literature two times by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b, 2019a). Third report for Albania. Distribution. The range of distribution for the present species spans across Europe from Portugal to the Caucasus and Asia Minor (Fibiger & Hacker, 2007).

Subfamily Hadeninae Guenée, 1837

Mythimna vitellina (Hübner, 1808). Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks. Found in the work of Rebel & Zerny (1931). This species is widespread and common in Albania (Moucha, 1963b; Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Mythimna unipuncta (Haworth, 1809). Material: 1 adult on location D. Arrived to the main sheet. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. This migratory

species was reported new for Albania in the work of Heinicke (1965). Several sightings and mention in literature followed (Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b; Bond, 2023).

Mythimna sicula (Treitschke, 1835). Material: 2 adults on location A. Arrived to the main and supplementary sheet. Remarks. Initial finding of the species in Albania was reported by Heinicke (1965). Further data on this species are provided by Stoyan Beshkov and his co-authors (Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov & Misja, 1995; Beshkov et al., 1996, 2020a, 2020b; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a).

Mythimna albipuncta (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks. Appears in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). A common species with well-established populations in Albania (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Mythimna ferrago (Fabricius, 1787). Material: 1 adult on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. This species appears in the checklist compiled by Rebel & Zerny (1931) but without proper location data. Heinicke (1965) also mentions the species but refers only to the previously reported specimen. Misja (1980) provided more reliable data regarding *Mythimna ferrago* from Albania with numerous observations. The species has not been reported since from the country, although it was found in numerous localities by S. Beshkov. Third report for Albania. Distribution. Widespread species, with its native range spanning across Europe, through the Near East and Asia Minor ending in Central Asia and in the western Himalayas (Hacker et al., 2002).

Mythimna l-album (Linnaeus, 1767). Material: 2 adults on location A and 1 on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already mention the species from the country. Its appearance in several following works with high abundance indicates that this species can be frequently found in Albania (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Anapoma riparia (Rambur, 1829). Material: 1 adult on location D. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. Beshkov (1995) reported this species as new to the Albanian fauna. Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b) published supplementary data. The last

mention from the country is tied to Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova (2025). Fourth report for Albania.

Tholera cespitis (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks. In Albania reported from Pogradec, between Dardhas and Guri i Kamjes; Prespa e vogel near Tren (Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025). The only previous report by Rebel & Zerny (1931) for Plav concerns Montenegro and not Albania (Heinicke, 1965). Second report for Albania. Distribution. The species can be found across Europe, from Spain reaching the Middle East, western Siberia and even China (Hacker et al., 2002).

Tholera decimalis (Poda, 1761). Material: 2 adults on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. The first report of this species from Albania is in the work of Misja (1976). Misja (1980) also mentions the species but only refers to the previously published data. Additional reports of the species from the country can be found in the work of Płóciennik et al. (2009) and Beshkov & Nahirnić (2019a). Fourth report for Albania.

Subfamily Noctuidae Latreille, 1809

Peridroma saucia (Hübner, 1808). Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks. The oldest report for Albania is that of Rebel (1913). Several later reports confirm the presence of this species in Albania (Moucha, 1963a; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Euxoa temera (Hübner, 1808). Material: 1 adult on location A. Arrived to the main sheet. 1 male and 1 female were also found on location SB. Remarks. The first report of this species from Albania is linked to Beshkov (1995). Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b) provided additional data regarding *Euxoa temera* from the country, but no observation was published since. Third report for Albania. Distribution. The species is widespread in the southern part of Europe. It can be found from Portugal to Central Asia and the Near East (Fibiger, 1990).

Euxoa vitta hercegovinensis Schawerda, 1938 (Figs 11B–D). Material: 9 males and 2 females on location SB. Remarks. In Albania, this species is only known from Mali i Thatë (= Galičica Mts), above Korita (Bregas) Village (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018a). Second report for Albania. Distribution. While the

species has a wide-ranging distribution across Europe reaching into Asia, ssp. *hercegovinensis* is restricted to the Balkans (Fibiger, 1990).

Agrotis segetum (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 1 adult on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. The species is already mentioned in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). Given its pest status, *Agrotis segetum* appears in several works from Albania (Moucha, 1963a; Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Kullaj et al., 2005; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Agrotis trux (Hübner, 1824). Material: 2 adults on location A. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets. Remarks. Misja (1980) published the finding of the first known specimen from Albania. The species now appears in a few more works regarding the country (Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021).

Agrotis ipsilon (Hufnagel, 1766). Material: 1 adult near location A, 1 on location B and 2 on location D. Arrived to the supplementary sheet on location A and to the main sheet on locations B and D. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. The species appears in the work of Rebel & Zerny (1931). Similarly to *Agrotis segetum*, this species also has many reported occurrences from Albania (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Kullaj et al., 2005; Płóciennik et al., 2009; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Chersotis margaritacea (de Villers, 1789). Material: 10 adults on location A and 11 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each mentioned location. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. The first findings of the species in Albania are reported by Beshkov & Nahirnić (2018b). Additional data was made public soon after by the same authors (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a). The most recent observations of this species from the country are published by Beshkov et al. (2020a). Fourth report for Albania.

Standfussiana lucernea illyrica (Rebel & Zerny, 1932) (Figs 11E, 12F). Material: 1 female near location D. Found in the vegetation not far from the main sheet. 1 female was also found on location SB. Remarks. This subspecies was described from Albania by Rebel & Zerny (1931) in their checklist and was cited by Heinicke (1965). Additional reports

reveal its need for high altitude as all known well detailed occurrence in the country was above 1000 metres (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019b; Beshkov et al., 2020b; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025).

Noctua pronuba (Linnaeus, 1758). Material: Approximately 20 adults on location A, 20 on location B, 5 on location C and 10 on location D. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on location A and B, to the supplementary sheets on location C and to the main sheet on location D. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. Appears in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). This species has a wide distribution and is very common in Albania. Known from many surveyed locations (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1994, 1996; Beshkov & Abadjiev, 1996; Płóciennik et al., 2009; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Noctua fimbriata (Schreber, 1759). Material: Observed on location SB. Genitalia examined. Remarks. First reported from the country by Beshkov (1994). Very common species in Albania, but difficult separation from its sister species *Noctua tirrenica* Biebing, Speidel & Hanigk, 1983 makes it hard to identify (Beshkov, 1996; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Noctua tirrenica Biebing, Speidel & Hanigk, 1983. Material: Observed on location SB. Genitalia examined. Remarks. The oldest report for Albania is from Korabi, Pshtriik and Jablanica (Hacker, 1989), but the specimen reported as “*Agrotis (Triphaena) fimbria* L.” by Rebel & Zerny (1931) has turned out to be *N. tirrenica* as well, as explained by Beshkov (1995). Many other localities are known in Albania from the sea level up to more than 2000 metres (Beshkov & Misja, 1995; Płóciennik et al., 2009; Nahirnić & Beshkov, 2017; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020a, 2020b).

Noctua orbona (Hufnagel, 1766). Material: 1 adult on location A and 1 on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. The initial report of this species from Albania by Misja (1976) mentions *Noctua comes* Hübner, 1813 as a synonym for *N. orbona*. Therefore, the likelihood of misidentification is high as previously stated in the articles from Albania, where the authors gave more reliable data for this species (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020a, 2024; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025).

Noctua comes Hübner, 1813. Material: Approximately 5 adults on location A, 10 on location B and 5 on location D. Arrived to both the main and

supplementary sheets on location A and B and to the main sheet on location D. Was also found on location SB. Remarks. Rebel & Zerny (1931) already mention this species from several locations. Appears in many articles later on, indicating its stable presence in the country (Heinicke, 1965; Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020b).

Noctua interjecta Hübner, 1803. Material: Field observation on location SB. Remarks. Reported as a new species for the Albanian fauna from the Adriatic Sea Coast: Velipoja Beach near Shkodra and Curila near Durres by Beshkov (1995). Many other reported localities followed (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018b; Beshkov et al., 2020b, 2024).

Noctua janthe (Borkhausen, 1792). Material: 2 adults on location A, 1 on location B and 1 on location D. Arrived to the main sheet. Remarks. Beshkov & Misja (1995) reported the species as new to the fauna of Albania. As stated in the article, the specimen Misja (1976) reported as *Noctua janthina* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) turned out to be *N. janthe* after the examination of the genitalia. In contrast to older articles where the reports about *Noctua janthe* in the Balkan Peninsula are scarce, recent works show that this species appears more often than previously thought, conceivably its absence in previous reports was perhaps due to its difficult separation from *Noctua janthina* and *Noctua tertia* von Mentzer, Moberg & Fibiger, 1991 (Płóciennik et al., 2009; Beshkov et al., 2020a, 2024; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2025).

Noctua tertia von Mentzer, Moberg & Fibiger, 1991 (Figs 11F–G). Material: 1 female on location SB. Remarks. The oldest report from Albania regarding the species is from Shkodra Lake: Zogaj Village (Beshkov, 1995). Not a rare species in the country, known from more localities in North and South Albania (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2018b, 2019a; Beshkov et al., 2020a).

Xestia castanea michaeli Ronkay, Ronkay & Varga, 2024. Material: 1 adult near location A and 15 on location B. Arrived to the supplementary sheet on location A, to both the main and supplementary sheet and to bait on location B. 1 female was also found on location SB. Remarks. Even though this subspecies was described recently, the species appears in the literature from Albania several times (Rebel & Zerny, 1931; Heinicke, 1965; Płóciennik et al., 2009; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021, 2025).

Xestia xanthographa (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Material: 3 adults on location A and 6 on location B. Arrived to both the main and supplementary sheets on each mentioned location and was also attracted to bait on location B. Remarks. Already mentioned in the checklist by Rebel & Zerny (1931). This species has many reports from Albania (Misja, 1976; Beshkov, 1995; Beshkov & Misja, 1995; Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a).

Xestia cohaesa (Herrich-Schäffer, 1849). Material: 3 adults on location B. Arrived to the main sheet. 1 female was also found on location SB. Remarks. The species was first reported from Albania by Beshkov et al. (1996). Nahirnić & Beshkov (2017) reported the second occurrence. Additional reports reveal several new locations for this species in the country (Beshkov & Nahirnić, 2019a; Beshkov & Nahirnić-Beshkova, 2021).

Discussion

The total number of species observed during the collecting trips and reported above was 122, with three species and a genus new to the fauna of Albania. Nine species are reported for the second, eighteen species for the third and twelve species for the fourth time from the country. The localities of the Hungarian team with most species were locations A and B, most likely due to higher temperatures associated with elevation. The Lepidoptera observed on those localities were, on average, species with earlier flight periods than those found on higher altitudes with colder microclimate, resulting in the observation of species whose flight periods differ significantly in such a short timeframe. These results are further backed up by the observed species on location SB where the related expedition was conducted earlier resulting in the discovery of species that were found later on much lower altitudes by the Hungarian team. Among the observed species, most were found on habitats suitable for the development of their larvae, with few exemptions (e.g.: *Nothocasis rosariae*). The present results show that, although significantly improved, the level of research in Albania on nocturnal Macroheterocera still fall short of most countries in Europe. The authors advocate for further studies on this, and other insect groups in the country, because as exemplified by *Gortyna borelii lunata*, species with high conservation value might still be present in Albania without notice.

These species, usually with very local distributions require protection in order for their population to remain intact and contribute to the richness of the fauna. Mali me Gropa has proven to have a wide variety of Lepidoptera in the autumn period. The diversity at this and other aspects of the year should also be subject to future research to increase the number of known species from the area of the massif and the country itself, but also to collect comparative material.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor.

Author' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Botond Balogh: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, project administration, resources, supervision, visualisation, writing—original draft; Balázs Tóth: data curation, investigation, resources, visualisation, writing—review and editing; Áron Horváth: investigation, resources, visualisation; Stoyan Beshkov: data curation, investigation, resources, visualisation, writing—review and editing; Nimród Varga: conceptualisation, data curation, investigation, resources, writing—review and editing.

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